

ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA URFDAGI/MODA ISMLAR

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***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada urfdagi/moda ismlar haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilib, unga tilshunoslikda berilgan izohi tahlilga tortiladi. Shuningdek, ismlarning urfga kirishi bosqichlari ko'rsatib o'tiladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar.** Moda, urf, ismlar, imitatsiya, ismlar jarangdorligi, ijtimoiy qatlam, ismning ommalashishi, ism qo'yish*

Urfdagi yoki moda ismlar ma'lum bir davr davomida ma'lum bir ta'sir etuvchi omillar asosida urf bo'lgan ismlar hisoblanadi. Moda ismlar fenomenini yaxshi anglab olish uchun dastavval moda so'ziga izoh berib o'tishni joiz deb topdik. Moda atamasi ma'lum davr davomida urf bo'lgan, o'sha davr didini ifodalovchi hisoblanib, nemis olimi Simmel fikriga ko'ra doimiy o'zgarib turadigan imitatsiya ko'rinishlaridan biri sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

U ijtimoiy qatlam vakillarini o'zaro bir-biri bilan bo'glovchi bo'libgina qolmay, balki u turli ijtimoiy qatlamlarni o'zaro farqlash vazifasini ham bajaradi. Shu bilan birga moda elit qatlam tomonidan boshlab beriladi va boshqalar tomonidan ularga taqlid qilish, ergashish natijasida yuzaga keladi. Bunda diffuziya yuqoridan pastga qarab yuz beradi. Moda ismlarda urfdagi biror kiyim, narsadan farqli tarzda kommersial qiziqish mavjud bo'lmaydi. Moda ismlar inson didi bilan bo'lsada, lekin ularda foyda olish, manfaat kabilar mavjud bo'lmaydi (1.514).

Urfdagi ismlar yuqoridan pastga qarab tarqaladi, ya'ni jamiyatning elit qatlamidan quyi qatlami sari. Urfdagi ismlar ma'lum vaqt davomida ommalashib, so'ngra vaqt o'tishi bilan urfdan chiqib boradi.

Modadagi ismlarga xos xususiyatlardan biri bu ularning doimiy o'zgarib turishidir. Tilshunos olim Frankga ko'ra (1977), urfdagi nomlar so'nggi yillar davomida tug'ilishlar qaydnomasida ko'p bora takrorlangan ismlardir.

Shu o'rinda bir savol tug'iladi: Ismlar qanday urfga kirishi mumkin?

Ismlarning urf bo'lishiga turli omillar ta'sir etadi, ularni biz lisoniy va tilga bog'liq bo'lmagan turlarga ajratishimiz mumkin: ismning jarangdorligi, oson talaffuz etilishi, ma'lum ijtimoiy qatlamga xoslikni ifodalashi, bolaning qaysi xududda tug'ilganligining ifodalashi (Masalan: *Jumaniyoz* asosan Xorazm viloyatiga xos ism) va boshq.

Ismning urfga kirishi va tarqalish jarayonlarini turli davrlarga bo'lish mumkin. Nemis olimi Frank, shuningdek, Debus ham ismlarning modaga kirish davrlarini quyidagicha ifodalashgan(1.9):

1. Faza: Innovatsiya – ismning tanlanishi ommalasha boshlashi
2. Faza: Duffiziya – Ismning tezlik bilan ommalashishi
3. Faza: Adoptatsiya – urfdagi ismning keng miyosda tarqalish
4. Faza: Ismning ufrdan chiqishi

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, tilda ismlar jamiyat oynasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi va shu bilan birga jamiyatdagi o'zgarishlarga mos holda turli davrlarda turli ismlar urfga kiradi va shuningdek, ma'lum bir davrda urf bo'lgan ism vaqt o'tishi bilan yana urfga kirishi mumkin.

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